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Article

Unveiling An Efficient Framework for Predicting Flood Risk Areas, Using Earth Observatory Data, Google Earth Engine, and Multicriteria Decision Making-Analytical Hierarchy Process

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ABSTRACT

The flood risk in the Niger-East region of Niger State is increasingly becoming an annual event. Climatic shifts, land-surface modifications, and human socioeconomic factors are among the conditions that trigger floods. This study explores geospatial technology and multicriteria decision analysis-analytical hierarchy process (MCDA-AHP) to develop a flood risk prediction system that leverages Google Earth Engine to process remote sensing data directly influencing flood risk. Elevation, slope, drainage density, rainfall, soil, proximity to drainage, proximity to road, population density, flow accumulation, and land use land cover (LULC). The weightage assignment was performed using the MCDA-AHP technique. Flood risk classes predicted as very low, 13.82 km² (9.29%), low, 18.77 km² (12.61%), low – moderate, 111.97 km² (75.24%), high, 3.32 km² (2.23%), and very high, 0.93 km² (0.63%) of the study area, respectively. This research presents a flood emergency response system that highlights the impact of different prioritization criteria across multiple conditions. Therefore, integrating GEE to generate different flood-conditioning risk indicators, prioritized and ranked using MCDA-AHP, is crucial for developing an efficient methodological framework for flood risk prediction across a wide region, achieving 88% precision. Thus, effective for evidence-based decision-making by authorities, policy makers, and emergency response agencies.

KEYWORDS

Google Earth Engine, MCDA-AHP, GIS, remote sensing, flood prediction, Niger East.

1. Introduction

The ongoing increase in flood risk is attributed to shifts in precipitation extremes driven by climate change and human-caused activities. Floods, regardless of their type, are sudden inundation

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events that occur rapidly and vary in severity. These events are triggered by heavy downpours that exceed the surface's capacity to absorb water, leading to potentially devastating consequences depending on the runoff mechanisms involved. The impact of floods is often influenced by localized geographical features that affect interactions among the atmosphere, land-surface conditions, and hydrogeology (Halder & Bose, 2024; Milevski et al., 2025; Ozegin. Floods, as an annual threat throughout the human age, emerged as one of the most devastating natural hazards, causing damage to human societies globally (Yang & Khan, 2022; Khan et al., 2024; Tripathy et al., 2026). While there has been a notable global increase in the frequency of floods, developing countries, particularly Nigeria, are disproportionately affected by these hazards. This has resulted in significant losses of human life, infrastructure, stability, and the economy, estimated to exceed billions of United States dollars (USD) annually (Bahago et al., 2019; Echendu, 2020).

Furthermore, flood hazards are estimated to have displaced over 2.3 billion people and accounted for the deaths of more than 6.8 million people worldwide (Khan et al., 2024). Worsening climatic extremes, including precipitation anomalies and the continuous rise in sea level due to melting of ice in polar regions during the warm season (Ghomsi et al., 2025), are expected to exacerbate devastating flood events over time. Consequently, the socioeconomic, human, economic, and environmental impact is expected to continue to increase. The high flood intensity and chaotic nature of surface runoff with increasing precipitation input and duration, along with multiple influencing factors and the inability to estimate the surface runoff mechanism with precision, have been identified as transient conditions that complicate flood prediction modelling (Chukwuma et al., 2023). The ability to identify flood-prone zones with precision becomes pivotal in minimizing flood impacts on both the human landscape and life, and properties. It can significantly reduce damage and enhance emergency response by providing policymakers with a hybrid decision-making system. This reality demands an urgent paradigm shift in methodology to provide policymakers, emergency management agencies, and other stakeholders with a flood-monitoring tool as a mitigation strategy with high precision through constructive multilayer data integration.

Methodological development toward improving flood risk prediction and emergency management to alleviate the devastating impact of floods has led to the emergence of new frameworks for the application of multicriteria decision analysis (MCDA), Samanta et al. (2016); Pham et al. (2021); Bhuyan et al. (2024); Das (2025) for risk assessment and prediction. Therefore, the use of geospatial techniques is pivotal to the emergence of data integration platforms that provide relevant information for identifying flood risk zones at the regional scale. MCDA and GIS, which provide an ordinal ranking of different data fusion methods, explain the magnitude of the influences on flood occurrence, with sensitivity largely attributed to rainfall intensity. Countless studies have emerged in the literature related to flood risk and impact assessment using GIS and space-related data in the last few decades (Samanta et al., 2016; Brakenridge, 2018; Chukwuma et al., 2023; Bhuyan et al., 2024; Hossain & Mumu, 2024; Jodhani et al., 2024; Das, 2025; Ozegin & Ilugbo, 2025). These studies are a continuation of Horton and Strahler, who were foremost renowned for their work in stream morphometric analysis that enables flood mapping based on river-induced floods. Unfortunately, a flood of more devastating impacts has been recorded more frequently over the last 50 years (Tanoue et al., 2016; Duan, Xiong, Cheng, Li, et al., 2022; Duan, Xiong, Cheng, Wang, et al., 2022), disrupting the surface flow regime, river morphology, and hydrological channel pattern with severe consequences on the disruptive power (Jodhani et al., 2024). The emergence of the application of artificial neural networks (Aziz et al., 2014; Abdellatif et al., 2015; Khosravi et al., 2020) toward improving the integration of multilayer information that could improve prediction precision, thus enhancing flood-related emergency response patterns and controlling human loss in general, dominates current research toward effective precision mapping.

The application of MCDA and ANN in flood risk mapping is driven by the need to integrate more layers of information into geospatial environments that reflect boundaries and enable visualization at the regional scale (Devi et al., 2025). In addition, data integration Chakraborty & Mukhopadhyay (2019); Souissi et al. (2020); Gupta & Dixit (2022); Hossain & Mumu (2024); Ahmad & Gupta (2026) demonstrates an efficient method of improving the development of a conceptual framework that illustrates the efficacy of multiple datasets' handling capability, which is critical to flood attenuation at a varying scale. Data handling capability is made possible through advances in computing

technology (Izham *et al.*, 2010; Izham&Bashir, 2022), access to a large amount of flood-related data through the unitization of optical remote sensing (RS) that relies on the feature spectral response signature (Brakenridge, 2018; Farhadi & Najafzadeh, 2021; Belcore *et al.*, 2022), and the continuous availability of computer data storage, which provides the requisite information required for the improved precision of flood studies (Hossain & Mumu, 2024). Leveraging the development of RS and GIS capabilities for hydrological datasets has enabled highly efficient and accurate flood-risk level mapping. Automatic detection from raw remote sensing data has emerged as an effective methodology that is changing the frontier of flood risk mapping in a GIS environment, owing to the continuous availability of high-resolution multispectral imagery from various space-based platforms. Such products include the Landsat thermal infrared radiometer spectrometer and ordinary land imager (Landsat 8-9 OLI/TIRS), and the advent of the Sentinel series, with an average revisiting period of 11 days (Geudtner *et al.*, 2021), thus enabling near-real-time flood monitoring. Evaluation of flood mitigation systems depends significantly on precise predictive maps for identifying susceptibility regions.

Current research shows that the most reliable systems are those that can quantify priorities across multiple conditioning factors, shifting focus towards improving prediction-precision methods. The strategy employed incorporates parameter weights calculated from the judgmental consistency of the factors' impacts in the flood-induction scenario. The use of multiple flood-related data fusion techniques through parameter weighting and the production of vulnerability and risk maps, but not limited to the use of random forest (RF), logistic regression, ANN, support vector machine (SVM), decision tree model, and Nkeki *et al.* (2022), within the GIS framework, and the integration of MCDA-AHP (Nkeki *et al.*, 2022) within the GIS framework applied in the decision-making process for selecting optimal alternatives across approaches were widely implemented in the decision-making process toward selecting optimal alternatives from a wide range of criteria (Devi *et al.*, 2025; Tripathy *et al.*, 2026). Today's research shows evidence of MCDA, GIS, remote sensing, and other predictive modelling algorithms in the development of high-precision flood-risk prediction systems for hazard mitigation (Chukwuma *et al.*, 2023; Devi *et al.*, 2025). The efficacy of these techniques is widely attributed to their simplicity, reliability, and ease of data collection, enabling the quantification of priorities across multiple related conditioning factors. In the same vein, the use of AHP effectively addresses multifaceted issues by providing a framework for selecting the most significant influencing factors of flood development among other considered criteria (Jodhani *et al.*, 2024).

However, the limited literature has led to only a few studies exploring the constructive gauging of data for flood risk prediction, and to the development of an efficient method for multilayer data construction that relies strictly on cloud computing for processing remote sensing information. The indicators selected using AHP-MCDA methods for integrating multivariate layers of information are critical to flood occurrence. This approach has limited efficiency in managing the interactive union potential explored by the AHP-MCDA approach to infer risk levels within the GIS framework, due to the limitations of other subset members that constitute the decision-making process. Recently, there has been a continuous emergence of cloud-based computing on GEE platforms; a relatively small amount of flood-related information was explored to determine their level of union within the predictive community as referenced in the work of Gxokwe *et al.* (2022); Antwi-Agyakwa *et al.* (2023); Waleed&Sajjad (2023), resulting in the redundancy of AHP-MCDA data handling capability (Adiat *et al.*, 2013; Mogaji, 2016). Research such as Adeyemi & Komolafe (2025) demonstrated the potential of the AHP-MCDA model to handle up to seven parameters in predicting several natural disasters, yielding promising results. However, the emergence of GEE has yet to fully exploit its potential to accommodate a large number of relevant data inputs. The failure to integrate multiple data sets into the GEE predictive model development system in contemporary flood hazard research, according to Bouramdane (2024); Caceres&Globa (2025), is not due to the limitation of the algorithm used but due to the lack of a unique conceptual framework that could effectively handle the different flood-related information that allows for the evaluation of potential risk level. This research addresses that gap by leveraging the availability of multiple cloud-based RS datasets and GEE computing power to generate an efficient flood-risk-level vulnerability map for secure flood-risk management.

The focused region comprises nine (9) local government administrative areas of the state that have been consistently devastated by flooding. The main objectives of this research are to under-

stand the influences of multiple factors on the flood occurrence process from the GEE platform, implement weightage overlay in AHP-MCDA to produce a robust approach for understanding the process of combining high-resolution remote sensing datasets for GIS flood hazard risk level mapping, and finally, explore the predictive flood risk sensitivity parameter across the Niger East region. Furthermore, weighted risk overlay mapping was explored in ArcGIS 10.8 as a crucial approach for prioritizing risk-conditioning factors, and the resulting flood-risk map was then overlaid on the region's topographic map to identify critical communities requiring heightened emergency response and relief activities during flood mapping.

2. Methodology

The development of an efficient method for flood risk mapping employed a combination of 10 flood-protégé causative and vulnerability indicators: soil, elevation, LULC, population density, distance from river, Proximity to the road, drainage density, lithology, precipitation, flow accumulation, and slope, as illustrated in Figure 1. The sources of data used in this study are provided in Table 1. The MCDA-AHP technique was employed to assign weights to all 10 parameters; the eigenvector, consistency matrix, and indices were used to prioritize the flood risk mapping. GEE, spectral indices of various causative and vulnerability factors, which were prioritized to maintain data homogeneity and ranked using AHP as an efficient methodology, thereby promoting a hybrid flood risk prediction with greater precision across the Niger East region.

2.1. Flood Risk Prediction Inventory Data

The inventory of flood risk predictive indicators for this research was categorized into physical, climatic, hydrological, and environmental conditioning factors. For the preliminary analysis, a soil map of the study area was retrieved and converted into a thematic dataset. This process utilized GIS tools to characterize the spatial distribution of soil types across the Niger East region. Soil properties are a fundamental determinant in flood risk prediction; specifically, areas dominated by sandy soils facilitate rapid infiltration and are generally less susceptible to surface runoff. Conversely, regions characterized by low effective porosity and poor hydraulic conductivity become significantly more prone to flood events. This thematic soil map is essential for evaluating the soil-hydrological behaviours that drive flood generation across the landscape. Physical conditioning parameters, including elevation, slope, flow accumulation, and drainage networks, were derived from Shuttle Radar Topography Mission (SRTM) Digital Elevation Model (DEM) data via the Google Earth Engine (GEE) cloud computing platform. The adoption of GEE was necessitated by its versatile and efficient down-scaling capabilities for geospatial analysis when working with multi-date datasets.

The generated slope map provides a comprehensive overview of gradient variations, while drainage information was extracted through GEE and exported to ArcGIS 10.5 to generate a drainage density map. Similarly, a flow accumulation map was produced using GEE, which provides a robust environment for precise data downscaling within regional boundaries. Climatic factors were addressed by preparing an up-to-date rainfall map using CHIRPS pentad data processed within GEE. The platform was selected for its efficacy in high-precision spatial rainfall mapping. To enhance the reliability of the output, supplementary data from the Nigerian Meteorological Agency and the Agricultural Development Agency were integrated into the spatial model. Furthermore, Land Use/Land Cover (LULC) composition, a primary driver of flood risk, was classified using Landsat 8 surface reflectance imagery. The pre-processing workflow included atmospheric noise correction and radiometric calibration, followed by the implementation of a Random Forest (RF) algorithm for image classification. In LULC classification, GEE enables seamless integration of ground-control data with current land-surface maps. For this study, a 70/30% data split was adopted: 70% of the training data was utilized to train the machine learning model, while the remaining 30% was reserved for validation. The accuracy of the classification was verified using a correlation matrix and the Kappa coefficient. Finally, proximity to drainage systems and infrastructure was determined by cross-ref-

erencing topographic maps with Google Earth imagery in ArcGIS 10.5. Google Earth served as a high-resolution validation tool for updating topographic sheets and providing current land-surface data. Regarding socio-economic factors, population data were retrieved from the Niger State Census Information (https://citypopulation.de/en/nigeria/admin/NGA027__niger/) and harnessed to develop a population density map. Collectively, these processed conditioning factors extracted in Table 1 serve as essential indicators for visualizing flood risk patterns and identifying the geographical vulnerabilities of the Niger East region.

2.2. AHP-MCDA

To assess the critical elements as conditioning criteria for flood risk, this study used the Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) (Saaty, 1988). AHP is a conceptual framework that uses pairwise comparisons and expert judgment to determine the propriety of weight scales for ranking alternatives (Saaty, 2004). GIS practitioners have widely used AHP-MCDA in recent years to integrate several flood risk elements and prediction indicators (Saaty, 2004). Slope, elevation, soil type, LULC, flow accumulation, drainage density, population density, distance from the drainage network, and distance from the road were all used in this study's AHP-MCDA process for flood risk mapping (Kolawole Abdulnafiu Adiat *et al.*, 2013; Bashir *et al.*, 2020; Mukherjee & Singh, 2020; Souissi *et al.*, 2020; Pham *et al.*, 2021; Hossain & Mumu, 2024; Ozegin & Ilugbo, 2025). To effectively incorporate the heterogeneity of the ten selected factors into the AHP model, equal interval, natural break, manual and same thematic classification (Mendas, & Delali, 2012; Hossain, & Mumu, 2024; Roy *et al.*, 2025), was adopted to provide framework for handling the unique behavior of each parameter This is important to preserve the input data attributes in other to examine their potential impacts on flood scenario. The implementation of this technique, according to Adeyemi & Komolafe (2025), Bashir *et al.* (2025), and Roy *et al.* (2025), allows data to respond to the condition under study rather than downscaling, which could alter the percentage contribution and thus affect reliability and precision. The initial phase of the AHP implementation in this study entails constructing a decision hierarchy, assessing the relative Weight of Evidence (WoE) for each conditioning attribute, and rigorously evaluating the consistency of the subjective evidence, following the protocols established by Kolawole Abdulnafiu Adiat *et al.* (2013); Bashir *et al.* (2020); Mukherjee&Singh (2020); Souissi *et al.* (2020); Pham *et al.* (2021); Hossain&Mumu (2024); Ozegin&Ilugbo (2025). Each flood-conditioning factor was assigned a priority weight using a 1–9 preference scale, as developed by. This approach facilitates the conversion of subjective qualitative judgments into a structured numerical framework for the AHP analysis.

The set of flood causative criteria (c) as $\{c_j | j = 1, 2, \dots, n\}$ (1)

The comparison matrix was obtained by combining the multiple parameters in equation (2)

$$\begin{bmatrix} 1 & f_{11} & f_{12} & \dots & f_{1n} \\ 1/f_{21} & 1 & 1/f_{23} & \dots & f_{2n} \\ 1/f_{41} & 1/f_{42} & 1 & \dots & x_{2n} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \dots & \vdots \\ 1/f_{n1} & 1/f_{n2} & 1/f_{n3} & \dots & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} w_1 \\ w_2 \\ w_3 \\ \vdots \\ w_n \end{bmatrix} \quad (2)$$

To obtain the eigenvalue, equation (3) was used

$$\lambda_{max} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \left(\frac{\sum_{i=1}^n \text{row entry of AW}}{\text{i}_{th} \text{ entry of row}} \right) \quad (3)$$

To determine the difference between the λ_{max} eigenvalue of the pairwise comparison matrix and the conditioning factors influences were achieved from (Saaty, 2008) equation (4)

$$CI = \frac{\lambda_{max} - n}{n - 1} \quad (4)$$

Where n=condition parameter, λ_{max} = Eigen vector value of the pairwise comparison matrix from (3).

In the application, a CI value below 0.1 is considered consistent and requires re-evaluation of the required criterion weightage. The consistency evaluation criteria involved a rigorous execution of

each factor, with all pairwise comparisons considered valid, if the CI value falls within the acceptable range of 0.1, with a maximum tolerable inconsistency value of 10% determine using equation (5)

$$CR = \frac{CI}{RI} \tag{5}$$

Where *CI* represents the consistency index, *RI* represents the random consistency index with a value of 0.04, for *n*=10 (Saaty, 2008).

Consequently, Weighted overlay analysis was performed using equation (6) to generate a Flood Risk Susceptibility (FRS) prediction map.

$$FRS = \sum_{i=1}^n W_i R_i \tag{6}$$

where,

W_i = weight of the flood predictive parameter *i*, and R_i refers to the score rating of parameter *i*, and *n* represents the total number of criteria. The normalized weighting of each selected criterion and the potentiality parameters relative to each criterion were then calculated to obtain the total weights of the different factors using a weighted linear combination approach in equation 6 (Singh & Ramiya, 2024; Hussain *et al.*, 2025).

Table 1. Meta dataset used for the generation of predictive model parameters.

Sn	Dataset	SR	Derived information	Source
1	Landsat 8-9 operational Land Imager/Thermal Infrared Sensor	30m	LULC	https://earthexplorer.usgs.gov
2	Digital Elevation Model	30m	Slope, basin, and drainage	https://cmr.earthdata.nasa.gov
3	Climate Hazards Group InfraRed Precipitation with Station (CHIRPS)	0.5°	Rainfall	https://chc.ucsb.edu/data/chirps
4	Shuttle Radar Topography Mission (SRTM)	30	Slope, Elevation, Flow Accumulation, Drainage Network, Distance to The River	https://cmr.earthdata.nasa.gov
5	Topo sheet	1:50,000	Names of vulnerable communities	GRID3 Nigeria https://earth.google.com/web/@9.25293667,6.68491483,269.75679234a,39781.42039417d,35y,0h,0t,0r/data=CgRCAggBOgMKATBCAggAS-g0I_____ARAA
6	Google Earth Imagery	-	Names of vulnerable communities	https://citypopulation.de/en/nigeria/admin/NGA027__niger/
7	Niger State Census Information by LGA	-	Population density map	https://hub.arcgis.com/datasets/CSI::nigeria-soils-data/explore?layer=2 retrieved on the 7 th January, 2026.
8	Soil	-	Soil information	

Note: SR: Spatial Resolution, LULC: Land Use Land Cover

Figure 1. Implemented RS, GEE, GIS and MCDA-AHP methodology workflow

2.3. Study Area

The study area of this research is the Niger-East (Figure 2) region of Niger State, between 9°38'21.41" and 10°5'44.22"N and 5°56'16.07" and 7°20'28.14"E. The Niger-East political region comprises 9 local government administrative areas, namely: Paikoro, Chanchaga, Bosso, Suleja, Tafa, Munya, Rafi, and Shiroro. The region covers an estimated area of 6,791.23Km². The general slope of the terrain shows a continuous rise from the SW to the NE, reaching a maximum elevation of 750m above mean sea level. The study area experiences a tropical savanna climate (Aw) with a wet season from May to October, during which an average of 1,200mm of rainfall is received per annum. During the dry season (November – March), dusty harmattan of Saharan origin dominates the study area, characterized by the absence of precipitation, and temperatures hover between 22 °C and 33 °C. The hydrography of the Niger East is drained mainly by the River Kaduna, which runs from NE to SW with several smaller tributaries. The river is dammed at Shiroro and Zungeru primarily for Hydroelectric Power Generation (HEP), which encourages the development of dam-induced flooding in the study area. Culturally, the study area is inhabited mainly by Gbagyi, Kambari, Kamukwu, Kadara, Koro, Hausa-Fulani, and some isolated Nupe traditions. These people predominantly depend on the land and forest resources for their livelihood, practicing subsistence agriculture. The variation in slope and the abundance of isolated pools of water within the river channels provide irrigation, ensuring the region's agricultural productivity year-round. Despite the potential of slope variation, flash floods during rainfall events are a common hazard in the river catchments of this region. The maximum rainfall received during August-September exceeded the average threshold of 1,300mm per hour, leading to excess runoff that favored flood generation. Niger-East, with a population density exceeding 210,000, faced a severe flood risk amid increased precipitation. Therefore, continued precipitation could exacerbate flood risk and thus disrupt infrastructure, agricultural lands, human settlements, and increase the risk of disease outbreaks, as major consequences for the communities. To mitigate the impact of flooding in this region, there is an urgent need to develop a flood predictive model that leverages access to critical risk-induced information, using state-of-the-art technol-

ogy, to understand the quantum and spatial scope of the disaster and promote resilience in flood management.

In the last two decades, the Niger-East region has experienced more than 30 flood events, with casualties ranging from mild to severe across the local government areas. Suleja, Tafa, Minna, Paikoro, and Kagara, for example, experienced several flood events during the period under review, with more than 300 casualties between 2017 and 2018. Furthermore, Shiroro and Munya suffered their most devastating impact of flooding in the years 2017, 2018, 2019, and 2022, with lives lost estimated to be over thirty. In terms of socioeconomic impact, in 2019, flood events destroyed over 20.37 km². By July 2025, these local governments had suffered more devastating floods than in previous records. The Minna metropolis, on the other hand, becomes the most severely flood-hit in 2019, with lives lost estimated at over 25 and properties worth billions of naira destroyed. The 2026 flood outlook from the Nigerian Hydrological Survey and the Nigerian Meteorological Agency indicates a higher flood risk than in the previous year, largely due to climatic shifts. Therefore, the development of a flood risk prediction system for the management and mitigation becomes imperative. This system could improve efficiency in emergency preparedness and risk mitigation. The development of this system could enhance authorities and policymakers with an effective tool for resource distribution during flood events in the study area.

Figure 2. Location of the study area; inset (a) Nigerian, Niger State, and Nigeria, (b) Niger state and the study area, and (c) the Study area.

3. Results

This research leverages an integrated approach, coherently combining the 5 thematic classes of flood-induced conditioning and factors that influence risk hazard refined via GEE datasets. This process, along with the AHP-MCDA, GIS, and RS techniques, enables the rigorous weighting of the ten (10) parameters for mapping of flood risk across the Niger East region. The produced FR map

was reclassified into very low (VL), low (L), moderate (M), high (H), and very high (VH) risk levels, and the communities at risk within Niger East were identified. The implementation of this approach, along with the flood-induced conditioning factors, provides insights that contribute to the development of a concise flood risk map to understand areas of severity across the study area.

3.1. Elevation

The elevation distribution map is presented in Figure 3. The results show that elevation varies across the study area. Five (5) classes of elevation were produced as: 0-230m as the lowest across the study area, followed by 230 - 310m, 320 - 400m, 410 – 480m, and 490 – 750m as the maximum elevation in the study area. In flood modelling, high-elevation areas are often associated with high surface runoff due to their elevation profile, characterized by poor infiltration and low soil saturation, resulting in a lower flood risk than in lowland areas, where runoff converges, and flood occurrence is higher. In application, the five (5) classes of elevation correspond to very low, low, medium, high, and very high. Such that, the operational weighing of the criteria for AHP-MCDA analysis (Table 2), low-land areas (0-230 m) was scored 5 indicating very high-risk level, 4 was assigned to 240 – 310 m, 3 was assigned to moderate elevation of 320 – 400 m, while value of 410 – 480 0m was scored 2 representing low and 480 - 750 m was scored 1 as reciprocal to the lowest flood risk with very low occurrence potential. Floods generally exhibit high risk in lowland areas, whereas highland areas often pose little or no flood risk. Historically, the issues of river presence, disappearance, emergence, and re-emergence could significantly influence the impact of elevation in flood risk mapping. Conversely, the study by Kader et al. (2024) indicates that elevation is the most important factor among flood-inundation parameters; this view is reliable only for river-powered floods.

Figure 3. Elevation distribution map of the study area.

3.2. Slope

The resultant slope map of the study area shows that Niger East (Figure 4) is characterized by hilly and lowland terrain, ranging from 0.0 to 51.14%. The slope distribution in the Niger East shows significant variation, ranging from a minimum of 0.0 to a maximum of 75 percent rise across the study area. Although slope is the gradient between two adjacent points, the obtained results show a lack of consistency with elevation across the study area. The lowest slope percentage rise was between 0.00 – 1.81%, followed by 1.81 – 4.21%, 4.21 – 8.82%, 8.82 – 16.25%, and the maximum was 16.25 – 51.14%, respectively. In flood risk mapping, slope distribution usually provides an excellent indicator of the runoff zone, reflecting differences in gradient. Slope steepness influences surface runoff velocity and direction, which can significantly alter the accumulation of runoff water on the surface, thereby serving as viable points for flood development. However, pedology, surface condition, and climatic variables are likely to alter the influence of slope (Kaya. Slope, compared to elevation, plays a critical role in flood modelling because these conditioning factors significantly direct/redirect surface runoff, affect the rate of soil saturation, and influence flow accumulation for flash-flood development. Infiltration from the adjacent slopes raises groundwater levels, increasing the rate of surface saturation and thus increasing the potential for flood risk.

Figure 4. Niger east slope percentage map.

3.3. Distance from the Road

The distance of areas from the road network per kilometer produced from the Euclidean linear distance is presented in Figure 5. The obtained five (5) classes of distance from the road network: less than 5.8 – 45 Km²; the next was 46 – 85Km²; 86 – 120Km²; 130 – 160Km²; and the highest Euclidean distance from the road network was 170 - 200Km². The thematic distance from the road network map was directly proportional to the area's road network coverage. Areas that are closer to the road network produce relatively small distances from the road, while regions with less linear connectivity produce wider Euclidean distance values. The road network served as a runoff-generating region with low infiltration potential and high runoff velocity, due to the absence

of sink zones that could increase saturation. Construction of the road network, in addition, is associated with drainage, which serves as a conveyor belt that evacuates runoff from impervious surfaces that could overflow the channel, creating flood risk conditions. The ability of this drainage canal to increase flood risk is mainly a function of the drained dimension, slope, nature of the adjacent land surface, and rainfall intensity and duration. In urban environments, characterized by the prevalence of impervious and semi-impervious surfaces, poor runoff sinks occur on the ground during rainstorm events. Thus, a substantial proportion of the runoff water may not be dissipated into the soil but accumulates more, which eventually overflows the drainage conveyor and creates a splash flood condition. Compared to rural or nonurban environments, the availability of natural drainage, the absence of runoff contribution from buildings, and the presence of a natural runoff circulation mechanism make the environment less prone to flooding. Therefore, flood occurrences in rural environments are less associated with road network distance factors than in the urban heterogeneous system, where runoff evacuation capacity largely depends on urban stormwater management.

Figure 5. Distance from the road distribution map.

3.4. Soil

The results from the FAO/UNESCO soil processing were correlated with the soil map of Niger State, sourced from the Ministry of Agriculture. Five (5) major types of soil were identified as: loamy, alluvium sand, mixed clayed sand, and clayed loam sand (Figure 6). There is a trace of intercalation of clay with other soil groups that is relatively suitable for both cereal and root crop cultivation. The dominance of alluvial sand provides insight into flood potential and the socioeconomic activities that could alter the heterogeneity of surface runoff characteristics. Soil in flood risk mapping is not effective in flood initiation (Matthews *et al.*, 2024; Adeyemi & Komolafe, 2025; Biazar *et al.*, 2025). However, when collaborating with other flood conditioning parameters, such as rainfall amount and slope, could provide a useful conceptual framework for inferring risk zones that are critical to prediction precision. Therefore, clay and alluvium formations have poor void connectivity, which affects water transmissivity into the underlying zones. In the surface runoff mechanism, these kinds of soils become saturated within a short duration of rainfall (Mohamad Yusoff *et al.*, 2010; Wong

et al., 2025). Although in groundwater exploration, sandy clay is considered relatively suitable for delineating an aquifer because of the transmissivity factors, whenever they prevailed as overburden geology that determined the surface runoff mechanism process, it provides suitable ground for flood generation due to the water retention capacity factor (Mohamad Yusoff *et al.*, 2010; Balacumaresan *et al.*, 2024). Clay loam sand concentrated around the Bosso, Chanchaga, and Paikoro local government areas responds differently to flood conditions, especially in vegetated and urban environments. In a vegetated environment, water-holding capacity in this soil group is high, and the array of trees, grasses, and shrubs provides a shield against modification of hydrographic characteristics. However, in an urban heterogeneous environment, the water-holding capacity of these soil groups is largely determined by the behavior of the hydrographic pattern that provides water to these formations via surface runoff, as well as by soil surface conditions. Therefore, the rating for flood development employed in this research considered clayed and mixed clayed to have a greater affinity for flood occurrences and was scored higher. Conversely, clay-rich soils, such as mixed clayed soils, have lower infiltration capacity, leading to increased surface runoff velocity and greater flooding during short rainfall events, and are therefore assigned a higher weight than alluvium and sand formations.

Figure 6. Soil map of the study area.

3.5. LULC

Six (6) classes of LULC types of Niger-Easts were identified in Figure 7: water body, built-up, vegetation, outcrop, agricultural land use, and barren land, respectively. Agricultural land use dominates the study area, followed by built-up and other land-cover types. LULC exerts a significant impact on the surface runoff mechanism that can initiate flood occurrences either directly or indirectly. Flood events are more frequent in urban environments due to limited infiltration of runoff, caused by urban structures that impede surface runoff accumulation, which eventually form splash floods (Junk *et al.*, 2024; Hamaamin *et al.*, 2025; Sehrawat. In a vegetated environment where such obstructing structures are absent, allow free runoff (Junk *et al.*, 2024; Abata *et al.*, 2025). In this study,

built-up LULC, characterized by impervious surface features such as roads and buildings, exhibits limited water infiltration and is associated with high runoff rates during rainfall events. This increases water flow velocity and volume, which contribute significantly to flash floods in urban lowland areas. Agricultural land use, barren lands, and vegetation promote water infiltration and storage, with limited surface runoff velocity and influence on maximum flows, thereby affecting water delivery to downstream areas and discouraging flood development. Built-up areas are more susceptible to flooding due to the dominance of relatively impervious surfaces, which impede infiltration and create a suitable breeding ground for flash-flood generation. In addition, proximity to water bodies, including streams and rivers, and the presence of an effective drainage network to convey runoff from built-up structures could affect the precision of flood frequency estimates.

Figure 7. LULC types of Niger East

3.6. Drainage Density

The drainage density map, processed in a GIS environment, is presented in Figure 8. Six classes of drainage density were obtained from the produces map: 7.6 – 20Km², 21 – 32Km², 33 – 45Km², 46 – 57Km², and 58 – 69Km². The maximum stream network density occurred in the lowland areas. The spread of the drainage network system is crucial to the occurrence in any given location. Areas of higher drainage density indicate more stream channels for runoff, increasing flood risk potential. Conversely, a region with lower drainage density indicates a poor stream network, low surface runoff, and reduced flood risk potential. Flooding potential in a drainage area occurs when excess accumulated runoff from precipitation in the channel exceeds the evacuation capacity. The excess water begins to overflow into the overland areas, gradually creating a flash flood. Thus, continuous precipitation inputs increase the risk of transforming to a real flood condition, affecting properties and human socioeconomic activities along its path. Appraising flood risk from the produced drainage density map shows that the highest risk level is found in the lowland region, due to the drainage system's inability to effectively evacuate the greater surface runoff. Usually, overflow from the adja-

cent stream gradually merges with the other surrounding streams, increasing the flow volume, accumulating as the capacity of the drainage network is exceeded, and becoming overwhelmed during extended rainstorm events (Hossain & Mumu, 2024; Junk et al., 2024). However, the damming of the River Kaduna at Shiroro and Zungeru could influence flood attenuation around the dam communities, and thus not necessarily be due to the drainage capacity for runoff evacuation. Hydrographic characteristics of the dam area usually influence flooding when the reservoir storage capacity is exceeded, and the upstream area is overtopped with water (Hossain & Mumu, 2024; Junk et al., 2024; Adeyemi). The downstream of a reservoir is severely impacted by floods whenever excess water is released from the dams over a particular period. The two conditions often create a barrier that may affect flood risk potential prediction due to the inherent nature of water storage capacity and discharge volume. River networks generally overflow their banks due to increased precipitation over extended periods, and the closest point to the river becomes flooded, with flood intensity decreasing with distance.

Figure 8. Drainage density map of the study area.

3.7. Proximity to the drainage

The proximity to drainage, computed using Euclidean distance, is shown in Figure 9. The closest distance to the drainage network was 0.08– 1.1 km². next was 1.2 – 2.1Km², 2.2 – 3.1Km², 3.2 – 4.0 Km² and 4.1 – 5.0 Km². Generally, the closer an area is to the river, the greater the flood risk, and the potential for flood risk decreases with one move away from the river network (Pathak *et al.*, 2020). According to the literature, areas with a distance of less than 1.15 km² are at higher flood risk, and the risk factor decreases as one moves away from the river network (Adeyemi. Although proximity is critical, a stream’s capacity to evacuate excess water during extended, high-intensity precipitation could affect the 1.15 km² validity established by Pathak et al. 2020. The study by Saranya et al. (2025) clearly shows that the precision of flood risk mapping and prediction largely depends on the number of model inputs and the correlation value. Therefore, proximity to the river as a parameter is grossly inadequate to conclude about the flood vulnerable point (Adeyemi, & Komolafe, 2025;

Saranya *et al.*, 2025), but integration of other pivotal factors, such as the drainage itself, rainfall intensity and duration, and overland surface characteristics are among the multiple factors that could aid flood risk appraisal with high precision.

Figure 9. Proximity to drainage map

3.8. Rainfall distribution map

The rainfall distribution map of the study area is presented in Figure 10, classified into 5 major thematic layers: 94 - 98mm/year (very low), 99 - 100mm/year (low), 100 - 110mm/year (moderate), 110 - 120mm/year (high), and 120 - 130mm/year (very high). Variability in rainfall amounts over time between regions is crucial for determining flood risk in an area. The maximum rainfall received in the Niger east provides insight into varying saturation levels, drainage capacity, and surface runoff mechanisms across the overland areas, thereby increasing flood risk. In addition to surface runoff, rainfall plays a significant role in the hydrological cycle, where precipitation is returned to the atmosphere through evaporation and evapotranspiration; the rates of these processes depend on temperature (Adeyemi). Precipitation amount and duration emerge as significant parameters influencing flood potential, given the extended duration of high-intensity rainfall that can initiate flooding events. Therefore, areas experiencing heavy rainfall can be identified as potential flood hotspots, while low-intensity regions remain of low susceptibility. The ability to delineate a hotspot zone with precision could support flood-risk emergency-response preparedness. However, in the general application of modelling, rainfall amount is prepared according to variation using the thematic layer to assign weights proportional to the amount in a given area. In this study, areas with the highest precipitation are rated 5, indicating a very high flood risk, while the lowest amount is rated 1, representing very low flood risk. Therefore, areas of the highest precipitation value were scored 5, while score 1 represented low flood risk potential. The nature and amount of rainfall received in the study area increase flood risk potential with increasing rainfall intensity. This result from the rainfall factor indicates that, as the region moves further into the precipitation season, the incidence of flood risk increases.

On a spatiotemporal scale, the maximum amount of rainfall is received in the months of late June/July towards early October. During this period, the drainage network in this region is at maximum capacity due to high surface runoff volume from the overland to the channel. Extended precipitation triggers the drainage network to exceed its water-holding capacity, resulting in overland flow into the adjacent point, with severity increasing towards the channel. In the same vein, the adjacent soil and bare surfaces, in response to precipitation availability during this period, push the water table closer to the surface, thereby reducing the saturation time, leading to runoff, and eventually increasing flood risk potential in the Niger east. In the dry season (November to February/March), characterized by the absence of rainfall, an increase in evaporation and evapotranspiration due to excessive temperatures reduces drainage water volume, thereby reducing cases of overland flow. In the case of overland saturation, water lost from the land to the atmosphere increases the saturation time due to soil dryness, which could promote flood risk. Therefore, the appraisal of flood potential in the study area is most likely due to rainfall that drives and sustains the hazard. This result conforms with many of the flood modelling systems, including Hagos *et al.* (2022); Adeyemi & Komolafe (2025), and Ait Naceur *et al.* (2025). However, this result could also be degraded when flood-inducing factors depend not only on precipitation but also on the river system, as observed in the coastal region. In the coastal region, proximity to water bodies has proven to be crucial for flood attenuation, with high vulnerability as documented in the work by Hadipour *et al.* (2020) and Narendran *et al.* (2022). In Nigeria, coastal states such as Lagos are often associated with flooding as a result of seawater intrusion, which has caused the loss of property and lives, as revealed in the work of Akoteyon (2022). The issue of dam-induced flooding arising from water discharge to maintain reservoir integrity often results in flooding independent of rainfall. The experience of dam-induced flooding globally provided a useful conceptual framework that demonstrates the contribution of factors beyond rainfall. Availability of many factors, such as drainage density, distance from the stream network, and dam collapse, among several others. These numerous studies further demonstrate the risk of implementing a single-parameter flood risk prediction model and state that such a model is less likely to predict the risk zone with high precision (Ghosh *et al.*, 2023; Adeyemi & Komolafe, 2025).

Figure 10. Rainfall distribution map of the study area.

3.9. Flow Accumulation

The flow accumulation map presented in Figure 11 is a pivotal tool for developing flood risk maps, providing critical indicators of accumulation and runoff concentration across the region. Flow accumulation is a crucial component in understanding surface runoff pathways and points of increased water volume during a rainfall storm event. Integrating flood-conditioning drivers such as slope, LULC, and terrain provides the comprehensive information required for flood risk evaluation. In addition, the produce accumulation map provides insights into locations where water could converge and promote flash flood generation. The flow accumulation value represents the number of streams that drain into upstream cells, which eventually flow into other cells. Poor water contribution from the total upstream cell of 0 – 180,000 flowing through the cells. This area is mainly the highland or elevated parts of the study area, with high runoff velocity, low flow accumulation, and a lack of sinks, thereby creating poor flash-flood generation points.

Figure 11. Flow accumulation of the study area.

3.10. Population Density

The total number of people per square kilometer is crucial information for flood risk mapping. In this research, the population density map is illustrated in Figure 12, which provides comprehensive detail for assessing demographic influences on flood risk prediction. The population counts per square kilometer in the study area are 84,000 – 120,000; 130,000 – 150,000; 160,000 – 170,000; 180,000 – 200,000; and 210,000 – 240,000. Each population category was assigned a weight using the AHP-MCDA technique to be incorporated into the flood risk prediction system map. The result of this process offers an essential concept in evaluating the potential impacts of human vulnerability in flood occurrences. In application, the population density map, which, according to Jodhani *et al.*, (2024), provides a crucial insight into the identification of areas with high human concentration, aiding in the formulation of targeted management plans, resource deployment, and emergency response systems.

Figure 12. Population density of the study area.

3.11. Flood risk susceptibility (FRS) prediction

Ten parameters described in the preceding section were considered to influence the risk in the Niger East region of Niger state. These are elevation, slope, proximity to road, proximity to the river, soil, LULC, drainage density, flow accumulation, rainfall, and population density. A detailed description of these parameters is provided in the previous section. Leveraging ArcGIS 10.8, spatial thematic layer maps were fused into the modelling system, as described in equation 7, to generate Figure 13. The final FRS map is then generated using weighted-sum overlay techniques, as described in equation 7. The consistency index and ratio of

$$\{(elevation * 0.07) + (slope * 0.13) + (proximity\ to\ the\ road * 0.05) + (soil * 0.09) + (LULC * 0.10) + (drainage\ density * 0.08) + (proximity\ to\ the\ river * 0.11) + (flow\ accumulation * 1.9) + (rainfall * 0.17) + (population\ density * 0.10)\} \quad (7)$$

Finally, the overall consistency ratio (CR) of the 10 factors, as a validation metric that assesses the logical consistency of the pairwise comparison to ensure judgments are not biased, was obtained at 0.04 (4%). By interpretation, a CR of <0.1 is generally accepted, indicating valid parameter weight estimation (Mogaji, 2016; Elkheir *et al.*, 2025; Das *et al.*, 2026).

4. Discussion

The obtained weightage vector map using AHP-MCDA as a prerogative to their potential influence on the establishment of flood risk. As an operational term, 'risk' is used to describe communities that are exposed to flood danger due to prolonged precipitation resulting in the saturation of overland areas, producing more water on the surface than the infiltration capacity of the land surfaces. Therefore, the linear combination of the weightage score of flood-inducing factors used in

this study is presented in Table 2. Rainfall (0.18); slope (0.13); flow accumulation (0.10); LULC (0.09); drainage density (0.08); proximity to the drainage network and road was 0.11 and 0.10, respectively; while population density was 0.1, respectively. The AHP-MCDA approach was applied to generate normalized weights for all 10 parameters. The assigned weight to each processed parameter is considered a percentage fraction of the overall weight of all criteria, as established by the pairwise comparison matrix. A thematic layer describes the result of the produced flood risk map as “very low”, “low”, “low – moderate,” “moderate”, and “very high as the maximum vulnerability index presented in Figure 13. Inference from the assigned weights of parameters as inferred from their influences on flood risk in the Niger-East region. Consequently, insights into flood severity could guide decision-making on where and how to concentrate the emergency response system with high precision. Areas with high and very high flood risk are confined to the high-latitude zone of the study area, affecting mainly Gaworaka, Tafa, and the fringes of Kuseriki. Similarly, the low-moderate flood-risk vulnerability areas dominated the Niger east, situated near the main-stream channel from the River Kaduna’s tributaries, reflecting the high-risk potential of these areas during flood events. The peripheral region of the study area showed a transition from moderate to high risk, indicating the spatial extent of flood susceptibility beyond the immediate environment.

The spatial dimension revealed in this research is driven by elevation, soil, precipitation, and the amount of water available in the drainage network. The findings of this research align with the work of Hossain & Mumu (2024), revealing distinct flood categories across the Niger East region. Importantly, the very high-risk zone (Table 3) encompasses only 0.93 km², representing 0.63% of the total study area. The high flood risk zone covers 3.32 km², or 2.23% of the Niger East. In contrast to the very-high and high flood risk index, the low-moderate risk class covered 111.97 km², constituting 75.24% of the Niger East. Conversely, the low-risk class covers 18.77 km², or 12.61% of the study area. In comparison, the very-low flood-risk class across the study area was smaller than the very-high-risk class but larger than the low, low-moderate classes, such that it represents a fraction of 9.29% of the Niger East. In flood risk events, emergency preparedness and response time, which, according to Hossain & Mumu (2024), is performed under intense pressure, play an important role in reducing vulnerability to life and property in real time. Furthermore, risk mitigation is crucial in emergency preparedness, especially regarding routes, security network coverage, proximity to healthcare facilities, and access to hard-to-reach communities. Furthermore, to minimize causality and improve the security of lives and properties during a flood accompanied by a heavy downpour, the very-high-risk classes zone requires the development of a specialized level of experts in emergency management operations. To mitigate flood risk in the study area, the appropriate design, construction, and maintenance of the existing drainage network are crucial. Moving forward, the results of this study underscore the imperative for policy-makers to prioritize risk reduction strategies rather than relying solely on emergency response and management during events.

The flood risk map produced in Figure 13 offered a crucial tool for risk preparedness and mitigation. It provides a useful decision-support tool by visualizing the most severely at-risk communities during flood events. This decision map provides authorities such as Nigeria’s national emergency management agency and Niger State’s emergency management agency with the capability to develop emergency response plans for flooding with high precision, thereby promoting resilience in flood risk mitigation and management. It’s worth noting that the produced risk map implementation is beyond immediate implementation and can also serve as a feature decision-making tool for a long-term goal. The implementation of the risk map provides a means of flood risk mitigation for a population of over sixty-six thousand people across the nine local governments that constitute the Niger East region. Similarly, with a population density exceeding 144 km², the produce map provides a crucial factor in the development of an effective early warning system for precision emergency management.

This study, therefore, demonstrates the viability of GEE as a cloud computing platform for generating remote sensing data relevant to flood attenuation. Against this background, the developed techniques of GEE, AHP-MCDA, and GIS were able to map five varying classes of flood risk in the Niger East region of Niger State. The highest flood risk classes are located between Tafa and Suleja, while Pandogari, Fuka, and Chucuba were communities with low risk of occurrence. The implemented methodology clearly indicates that flood risk is more of a function of LULC characteristics

driven by extended, heavy, and continuous precipitation inputs that begin as flash floods. Thus, for flood risk management, surface drainage, the ability to predict precipitation volume, and other land-cover information are crucial for risk mitigation in the study area. The result of this study conforms with similar studies worldwide, including Bahago et al. (2019); Bashir (2022); Chukwuma et al. (2023); Adeyemi & Komolafe (2025), among several others. Finally, the result of this study implicated over 4 km² of the study area as being at high to very high risk of flooding. This demonstrates the efficacy and precision of the developed framework for mapping flood risk classes in the study area. In addition, the high-to-very high-risk classes required a concentration of more resources during flood hazard preparedness and emergency response. It's also crucial to note that an extended period of rain could alter these risk classes, leading to a transition between classes.

Figure 13. Predicted flood risk potential map of the Niger East.

4.1. Predicted flood risk validation assessment

To assess the predictive performance of the MCDA-AHP model in flood risk mapping, it is crucial to establish it as an excellent alternative in flood risk hazard studies. This study explored the collinearity of regression correlation as a validation technique. This technique produces an R^2 value in ArcGIS 10.8, where the randomly partitioned historical flood records (70:30%) were spatially determined from the predicted flood risk potential class shown in Figure 13. According to Figure 14, an accuracy of 0.88 was obtained, representing 88% prediction accuracy. The analysis of the prediction system performance in flood risk prediction is largely due to the nature and characteristics of the data that feed into the model. That was obliterated from the view that predicted food risk is a function of precipitation amount, the nature of the overland surfaces, and the prevalent channel characteristics. Using equation 7 and the GEE and GIS-based spatial analyst tools, the low-risk classes are identified. are driven by soil type, nature of LULC types and available precipitation volume.

Figure 14. AHP prediction accuracy assessment result.

Table 2. Flood risk predictors, criteria, and weight.

SN	Model Factors	Classes	Flood Risk	WoE	Weight	References
1	Elevation (m)	0 - 230	5	Very High	0.07	
		230 - 310	4	High		
		320 - 400	3	Moderate		
		410 - 480	2	Low		
		490 - 750	1	Very low		
2	Slope (%)	0.00 - 1.81	5	Very High	0.13	Equal interval (Sarkar <i>et al.</i> , 2022)
		1.81 - 4.21	4	High		
		4.21 - 8.20	3	Moderate		
		8.82 - 16.25	2	Low		
		16.25 - 51.14	1	Very Low		
3	Proximity to the Road (Km)	5.8 - 45	5	Very High	0.05	Natural break (Hos-sain, & Mumu, 2024)
		46 - 85	4	High		
		86 - 120	3	Moderate		
		130 - 160	2	Low		
		170 - 200	1	Very Low		
4	Soil	Loamy	4	High	0.09	Manual (Vojtek, & Vojteková, 2019)
		Alluvium Sand	2	Low		
		Mixed Clayed	4	High		
		Clayed Sand	3	Moderate		
		Clayed Loam Sand	1	Very Low		
5	LULC	Water Bodies	5	Very High	0.10	Same classification (Kader <i>et al.</i> , 2024)
		Built-up	4	High		
		Vegetation	2	Low		
		Outcrop	1	Very low		
		Agricultural Land Use	4	High		

	Barren Land	3	Moderate		Manual (Hossain, & Mumu, 2024)	
6	Drainage Density (sq km)	7.6 – 20	1	Very low	0.08	Same classification (Kader <i>et al.</i> , 2024)
		21-32	2	Low		
		33 – 45	3	Moderate		
		46 – 57	4	High		
		58 – 69	5	Very High		
7	Proximity to the River (Km)	less than 1	5	Very High	0.11	Manual (Sarkar <i>et al.</i> , 2022)
		1.20 - 2.10	4	High		
		2.20 - 3.10	3	Moderate		
		3.20 - 4.00	2	Low		
		4.10 - 5.00	1	Very Low		
8	Flow Accumulation (Pixel)	<180,000	1	Very Low	1.9	Equal interval (Sarkar <i>et al.</i> , 2022)
		180,000 - 700,000	2	Low		
		700,000 - 1,600,000	3	Moderate		
		1,600,000 - 2,700,000	4	High		
		2,700,000 - 8,400,000	5	Very High		
9	Rainfall (mm/year)	94 – 98	1	Very Low	0.17	Equal interval (Sarkar <i>et al.</i> , 2022)
		99 – 100	2	Low		
		100 – 110	3	Moderate		
		110 – 120	4	High		
		Greater than 120	5	Very High		
10	Population Density	84000 – 120000	1	Very Low	0.10	Manual (Jodhani <i>et al.</i> , 2024)
		130000 - 150000	2	Low		
		160000 – 170000	3	Moderate		
		180000 – 200000	4	High		
		210000 - 240000	5	Very High		

Table 3: Flood risk level and the area extent

Risk Class	Area (Deg)	Area (Km ²)	Percentage (%)
Very Low	0.1243514	13.82	9.29
Low	0.1688637	18.77	12.61
Low-Moderate	1.0073461	111.97	75.24
High	0.0298904	3.32	2.23
Very High	0.0083766	0.93	0.63
Total		148.81	100.00

5. Conclusion

Flood hazard is a natural hazard that dates back to the human age. The impacts are exacerbated by socioeconomic factors, poor urban planning, inadequate or poor drainage design, and the lack of a predictive system that could provide an early warning system for risk mitigation and management, rather than relying on vulnerability. The Niger East region in the state housed two major hydroelectric dams, and, with a population density of over 160,000, it became exposed to flood risk. Thus, this research proposed an efficient process of integrating ten flood risk indicators, including elevation, slope, rainfall, flow accumulation, soil, LULC, drainage density, proximity to road network, proximity to drainage network, and population density. The processing leverage on GEE, a cloud computing platform that provides spatial analytical capabilities, while emphasizing the integration of remote sensing and geospatial technologies for spatial visualization evaluation. MCDA-AHP techniques were employed to assign justifiable weightages and assess priority ranks, while each derived criterion weight was evaluated for consistency index and ratio. The flood risk zones of Niger East were delineated into five classes: very low, low, low-moderate, high, and very high. The prioritization of the flood-inducing risk-conditioning factors in the AHP process provides an efficient tool for developing flood risk planning and management across a large area. The application of GEE, spectral indices, and MCDA-AHP provides a robust tool that guides authorities in flood risk preparedness and mitigation.

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